

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: AFADODAN****FIRST NAME: Yaovi****PROGRAM CODE: DILT****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Kabiru**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.
The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)
The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references
The author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)
The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text

1. Persuade readers (EUCLID 2019, 1)
2. Viewpoint from different authors (EUCLID 2019, 2)
3. Avoid plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 6)
4. Consistent style (EUCLID 2019, 24)
5. Standard American English (EUCLID 2019, 27-28)
6. Chicago Manuel of Style (EULCID 2019, 44)
7. Avoid confusion (EUCLID 2019, 46)

ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

ACA-401/ACA-401D period one focused on essay writing. The main book devoted to this course is the ACA-401/ACA-401D coursepack revised by Cleenewerck Laurent and Kabiru Gulma.

The book contains a total of nine chapters. The first chapter is about essay writing (1-5). The second concern how to avoid the plagiarism (5-13). The chapters three, four, five and six (13- 34) are dedicated to some rules and steps to follow for writing a quality academic paper.

Specially the chapter seven of the book addressed sample corrections to paper, CMS crib sheet in chapter eight, and Latin abbreviations and expressions in chapter nine. This last chapter provides two tables showing common Latin abbreviations and expressions used by technical communicators.

The authors gave many examples and specially to enable students to make a better academic writing.

The coursework also included one video facilitated by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck.

2) THE MAJOR LESSONS LEARNED

Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma explained that “an academic essay aims to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence” (EUCLID 2019, 1). I agree that an academic essay aims to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence. It’s not a hollow speech devoid of any evidence. It’s a work of reasoning and demonstration based on evidence.

For better academic writing, we need to make sure that we understand the topic, do the research and organize our ideas and avoid plagiarism

a) Organizing and research of ideas

Successful academic writing requires organizing and researching the ideas to be developed. For me, I think that organization allows to structure the ideas and research allows to confront your ideas with those of other authors.

“Your essay should be balanced: that is, it should include a range of information and viewpoints from different authors that explore the key arguments and relevant aspects of a particular topic. Don’t only include evidence that agrees with what you are arguing; if there are different or opposing views, then they need to be examined” (EUCLID 2019, 2).

b) Avoid plagiarism

When we are writing papers, one of the most important things the writer should do is avoid plagiarism.

Plagiarism is a proof of intellectual lightness and a very heavy fault for any academic researcher. Everything possible must be done to avoid it. “In order to avoid plagiarism, the solution is to properly CITE the author or source that has provided the information you are using” (EUCLID 2019, 6). As a PhD student, I believe that these leads will help me enormously to avoid plagiarism in my thesis.

i) Writing style has to be consistent

EUCLID recommends the Chicago Rules and American English. No one style is superior to another. What must remain the common point of the styles is their coherence.

For the authors, “a style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent. Style guides are generally associated with certain types of writing like technical writing, commercial or business writing, journalism, and web copywriting. In each of these cases, there is a need to ensure that the writing style is consistent” (EUCLID 2019, 24).

Personally, I think that an author should be free to express his ideas in a coherent style that should be his own. The essential thing is to convince by consistent and logical reasoning.

ii) *Avoid confusion*

There are confusions to avoid when we write. “A re-creation is not the same as recreation. A fast-sailing ship is one designed for speed. A fast-sailing ship is one that made a fast passage” (EUCLID 2019, 46).

For me, these confusions can only be avoided if the author has a good command of the language in which he writes. The mastery of a language requires the mastery of spelling, grammar and conjugation.

EUCLID recommend Chicago Manual of Style (CMS). CMS is a simple style for writing theses, scientific and academic articles. “Chicago Style is the style of formatting books and research papers documented in the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS), 2003, and Kate Turabian’s Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, 1996 (both published by the University of Chicago Press). While sometimes reference is made to a “Turabian style,” this is simply the Chicago style applied to research papers. Revised Fall 2006” (EUCLID 2019, 44).

3) **CONCLUSION**

Successful academic writing requires organization and time for research and reading. It must be written in a recognized academic style. Euclid recommends CMS. One of the big mistakes to avoid in academic writing is plagiarism.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.